

1 **Title:** Pattern separation in the Hippocampus through the eyes of computational modeling

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11 **Key words:** computational models, dentate gyrus, granule cells, information storage, learning,
12 memory, mnemonic process

13 **ABSTRACT**

14 Pattern separation is a mnemonic process that has been extensively studied over the years. It
15 entails the ability -of primarily hippocampal circuits- to distinguish between highly similar inputs,
16 via generating different neuronal activity (output) patterns. The dentate gyrus in particular has
17 long been hypothesized to implement pattern separation by detecting and storing similar inputs
18 as distinct representations. The ways in which these distinct representations can be generated
19 have been explored in a number of theoretical and computational modelling studies. Here, we
20 review two categories of pattern separation models: those that address the phenomenon in an
21 abstract mathematical fashion and those that delve into the underlying biological mechanisms by
22 taking into account the anatomy and/or physiology of hippocampal circuits. We summarize the
23 strategies, findings and limitations of these modeling approaches in the light of new experimental
24 findings and propose a unifying framework whereby different network, cellular and sub-cellular
25 mechanisms converge to a common goal: controlling sparsity, the key determinant of pattern
26 separation in the dentate gyrus.

27 INTRODUCTION

28 The mnemonic process of Pattern Separation

29 The hippocampus, including its subregions dentate gyrus (DG) and areas CA3 and CA1, is known
30 to play a key role in learning and memory (Eichenbaum, 2000; Squire et al., 2004) and particularly
31 in episodic memory formation, storage and retrieval (Tulving, 2002). Episodic memory is the ability
32 to store and recall the memory of a specific event/experience, presumably by creating
33 associations between individual items experienced in a given context, e.g., a particular place with
34 an object or a person. To avoid confusion of similar experiences, the hippocampus has the ability
35 to distinguish highly overlapping episodes via the generation of distinct neuronal responses. This
36 computational process, commonly referred to as *pattern separation* (for recent reviews see
37 (Leutgeb and Leutgeb, 2007; Yassa and Stark, 2011; Schmidt et al., 2012; Rolls, 2013)), is critical
38 for normal brain functioning and is affected by various disease conditions accompanied with
39 cognitive decline, such as schizophrenia, Alzheimer's and aging (Ohm, 2007; Das et al., 2014).
40 The complementary function of pattern separation, namely the ability to fully retrieve stored
41 information given a partial or noisy stimulus, known as *pattern completion*, is also believed to be
42 implemented by hippocampal circuits (Kesner, 2013).

43 The term *pattern separation*, while typically used indistinguishably, often refers to two distinct
44 processes (Santoro, 2013): a) *behavioral pattern separation*, whereby an animal exhibits the
45 behavioral ability to discriminate between two items, namely the observations are *external* to the
46 brain (Clelland et al., 2009) and b) *neural pattern separation*, whereby the neuronal activity of a
47 brain circuit is distinct for two items, namely the observations are *internal* to the brain (Leutgeb et
48 al., 2007). Computational models deal with *neural pattern separation*, while experimental studies
49 describe mostly *behavioral pattern separation*. As *behavioral pattern separation* is observational,
50 it does not provide much information about the neural mechanisms underlying the organism's

51 discriminability actions. *Neural* pattern separation on the other hand, can reveal *where* in the brain
52 the separation function takes place (albeit not extensively) and shed light on *how* these behavioral
53 actions may be implemented. Experimental work involving concurrent behavioral assessment and
54 detection/manipulation of respective neuronal activity patterns would be ideal for probing pattern
55 separation yet such studies are scant, due to challenging technological limitations. In this review,
56 computational models are assumed to assess *neural* pattern separation while experimental
57 studies *behavioral* pattern separation, unless otherwise specified.

58 **Role of Dentate Gyrus in Pattern Separation**

59 The DG is the gateway to the hippocampus, through which incoming information from the
60 entorhinal cortex (EC) is passed to the CA3 subregion. Both theoretical/computational
61 (McNaughton and Morris, 1987; Treves and Rolls, 1992, 1994; O'Reilly and McClelland, 1994)
62 as well as experimental studies, using behavioral (Kesner et al., 2004; Rolls and Kesner, 2006),
63 neurophysiological (Leutgeb and Leutgeb, 2007; Leutgeb et al., 2007; McHugh et al., 2007) and
64 functional magnetic resonance imaging techniques (Kirwan and Stark, 2007; Bakker et al., 2008;
65 Lacy et al., 2011) have proposed that pattern separation is implemented primarily by the DG,
66 whereas pattern completion takes place in the CA3 area. Moreover, experimental studies suggest
67 involvement of the DG in pattern separation not only in rodents but also in humans (Leutgeb et
68 al., 2004, 2007; McHugh et al., 2007; Liu et al., 2015; Berron et al., 2016). Specifically, the
69 principal dentate neurons, the granule cells (GCs), have been hypothesized to fulfill this role
70 (Treves et al., 2008) due to their activity sparseness (Schmidt et al., 2012; Danielson et al., 2017;
71 GoodSmith et al., 2017), low firing rate (Danielson et al., 2016; Senzai and Buzsáki, 2017) and
72 sparse connectivity (Amaral et al., 2007). In addition, dentate GCs are among the few neuronal
73 types that undergo adult neurogenesis in the brain and newborn GCs are considered to play a
74 key role in learning and memory (Clelland et al., 2009; Appleby et al., 2011; Sahay et al., 2011a)
75 processes, including pattern separation (van Praag et al., 1999; Kesner and Rolls, 2015).

76 **Why care about computational models?**

77 Since there are several excellent reviews on pattern separation in general (Leutgeb and Leutgeb,
78 2007; Yassa and Stark, 2011; Schmidt et al., 2012; Santoro, 2013), we focus on presenting and
79 discussing the different *theoretical approaches* and *computational models* that have examined
80 the pattern separation function in the DG. It should be stressed that pattern separation and
81 completion are not exclusively associated with hippocampal regions. Cognitive processes such

82 as visual perception (Marr, 1982), object recognition by the perirhinal cortex (Gilbert and Kesner,
83 2003; Bartko et al., 2007a; b), emotional pattern discrimination evidenced in the amygdala (Gilbert
84 and Kesner, 2002) and olfactory discrimination by the piriform cortex (Haberly, 2001; Sahay et
85 al., 2011b), are all related to the generalized function of pattern discrimination. In this review we
86 focus on computational models of the DG as this subregion is the one most extensively studied
87 with respect to pattern separation, both experimentally and theoretically, compared to the
88 aforementioned brain areas.

89 Given the advent of technology that allows experimental investigations of both behavioral and
90 neural pattern separation, a natural question is “what computational models provide that
91 experiments cannot account for”. The answer is twofold: 1) the ability of computational models to
92 provide mechanistic insights of pattern separation implementation at the neuronal level and 2) the
93 ease with which models explore the entire parameter space in a quick and cheap manner so as
94 to guide the complicated and expensive experimental investigations. Here, apart from presenting,
95 comparing and discussing the different computational models, we try to infer the network, cellular
96 and sub-cellular mechanisms that affect pattern separation in the hippocampus so as to propose
97 a unifying view of this intriguing mnemonic process.

98 **ASSESSING PATTERN SEPARATION**

99 In animal experiments, pattern separation is typically measured by behavioral assessment
100 (behavioral pattern separation (Santoro, 2013)): animals are asked to perform a different task
101 depending on their interpretation of similar stimuli (Leutgeb et al., 2007; Nakashiba et al., 2012;
102 Kannangara et al., 2014). At the neuronal circuit level, discrimination between similar inputs can
103 be achieved via the generation of different activity patterns, either through the activation of distinct
104 sets of neurons or via the modulation of the firing rates in the same population of neurons (Leutgeb
105 et al., 2004; Deng et al., 2010, 2013). Similarly, in computational models, neural pattern

106 separation is typically measured through appropriate metrics that estimate the distance or
107 similarity between activity patterns. These patterns are usually expressed as binary neuronal
108 activity (ON / OFF) or neuronal firing rate vectors. **Figure 1** shows a typical schematic example
109 of pattern separation among two similar (highly overlapping) input patterns from the EC that
110 activate respective output patterns in the DG. The “population overlap” approach takes into
111 account the overlap of active GCs in the DG (output) compared to the EC input overlap, while the
112 “rate overlap” approach considers the different firing rates of the GCs that are active in response
113 to both input patterns. In both cases, pattern separation is deemed successful if *the two output*
114 *(DG) patterns differ to a larger extent than their respective input (EC) patterns.*

115 Note that even among computational models, neural pattern separation is measured in slightly
116 different ways. Some assess the difference in the overlap of input and output patterns (Myers and
117 Scharfman, 2009; Nolan et al., 2011) while not explicitly accounting for sparsity and network size,
118 while others calculate the corresponding distances in the input and output patterns (Faghihi and
119 Moustafa, 2015; Chavlis et al., 2016) taking such features into account. In general, the main
120 difference among these approaches lies in the metric used to quantify neural pattern separation.

121 **THEORETICAL APPROACHES TO PATTERN SEPARATION – A HISTORICAL** 122 **PERSPECTIVE**

123 The majority of theoretical models that examine pattern separation are derived from David Marr’s
124 mathematical theory of the cerebellum (Marr, 1969), where Marr proposed that the cerebellar
125 granule cells are able to create sparse representations of their sensorimotor inputs. Specifically,
126 cerebellar granule cells were proposed to receive highly overlapping information, which is then
127 transformed into highly sparse, independent representations in the granular layer. As a result,
128 incoming information is stored with minimum interference. In his subsequent study of simple
129 memory in the archicortex (Marr, 1971), Marr elaborated a similar mathematical model of

130 hippocampal function, consisting of binary neurons with binary synapses. Marr proposed that the
131 dentate GCs act as memory cells -by encoding the inputs from the EC- and propagate simple
132 representations of this information to the CA3 area. More than a decade later, Rolls formulated a
133 more extensive theory of the hippocampus in which dentate GCs functioned as a preprocessing
134 station before storage into the CA3, by performing pattern separation (Rolls, 1987).

135 Subsequently, using theoretical analysis and computational simulations, it was suggested that the
136 very large number of granule cells makes them an ideal substrate for pattern separation in DG,
137 as it is easier to create non-overlapping representations in large, sparse-firing neuronal networks
138 (Rolls, 1989a; Gibson et al., 1991). In agreement, using a two-layer neural network model
139 consisting of an input (EC) and an output layer (DG/CA3) and assuming that each granule cell
140 receives feedback inhibition from an interneuron, Gibson and colleagues proposed that keeping
141 granular activity at very low levels and reducing the amount of input connections in the granular
142 layer improves pattern separation ability (Gibson et al., 1991).

143 On the other hand, the CA3 was suggested to play a crucial role in forming new memories of
144 discrete events (Rolls, 1989a; b, 1990). As CA3 receives input from EC directly from the Perforant
145 Path (PP) and indirectly through the DG via the mossy fibers, it was proposed that the DG acts
146 as a “preprocessor” by orthogonalising its inputs before their storage in the CA3 (Rolls and Treves,
147 1990; Treves and Rolls, 1992). Using an analytical two-layer model of the EC (input layer) and
148 the DG/CA3 (output layer) with random connectivity and k-Winner-Takes-All (*kWTA*) type of
149 activation functions (Majani et al., 1989), it was proposed that DG sparsity facilitates pattern
150 separation (O’Reilly and McClelland, 1994; McClelland et al., 1995).

151 These early studies were the first to predict a role of the DG, and specifically for dentate GCs, in
152 pattern separation. They collectively pointed to GCs as responsible for separating the received
153 EC inputs in order to provide the CA3 subregion with highly sparse, non-overlapping

154 representations. As such, dentate GCs were proposed to serve as preprocessors of information
155 before its storage to the CA3 (Treves and Rolls, 1994; Hasselmo et al., 1995; Hasselmo and
156 Wyble, 1997). GCs are suitable candidates for this task as they are significantly more numerous
157 compared to EC and CA3 principal cells (Amaral et al., 1990), they fire sparsely (Jung and
158 McNaughton, 1993; Leutgeb et al., 2007; Danielson et al., 2016), they form few but strong
159 synapses on CA3 pyramidal cells (Rollenhagen et al., 2007), and undergo neurogenesis
160 throughout life (van Praag et al., 1999; Aimone et al., 2010). Several aspects of the proposed
161 theories have been updated and reviewed elsewhere (Rolls and Kesner, 2006; Kesner and Rolls,
162 2015), with researchers assigning more specific functions to the DG. For example, the dorsal DG
163 has been proposed to control spatial pattern separation (i.e. reduction of interference between
164 similar environments), while ventral DG to mediate odor pattern separation.

165 Many of the early computational predictions have been supported experimentally in both animal
166 models (Leutgeb et al., 2004; Leutgeb and Leutgeb, 2007; McHugh et al., 2007; Neunuebel and
167 Knierim, 2014) and human subjects (Bakker et al., 2008; Lacy et al., 2011; Ally et al., 2013; Berron
168 et al., 2016), suggesting that DG is indeed the key hippocampal subregion involved in neural
169 pattern separation, at least for the mammalian brain. While the abovementioned simple models
170 successfully captured the ability of the DG to transform overlapping input patterns into more
171 distinct ones, they could not point to specific cellular or subcellular mechanisms that underlie
172 pattern separation and its dysfunctions (e.g. under conditions such as temporal lobe epilepsy,
173 schizophrenia, Alzheimer's disease etc.). More recently, advances in computational processing
174 have allowed the development of more sophisticated neuronal network models able to delve
175 deeper into such mechanistic issues.

176 **DETAILED COMPUTATIONAL APPROACHES TO PATTERN SEPARATION**

177 Abstract computational models were the first to propose that the DG has the ability to perform
178 pattern separation via its GCs (Kesner and Rolls, 2015). However, the majority of these studies
179 relied on numerous simplifying assumptions, such as collapsing the hippocampal sub-regions
180 (e.g., EC and DG, DG and CA3) in black-box like structures and/or ignoring specific neuronal cell
181 types, their morphology and biophysics etc. In fact most of these studies treated neurons as
182 extremely simple binary devices. To counteract these limitations, a number of detailed DG, DG-
183 CA3 and/or entire hippocampal network models have been developed. These models often vary
184 greatly in their level of detail while still representing an abstraction of the biological reality.
185 However, they offer new insights into the possible mechanisms that enable pattern separation to
186 take place in neuronal circuits, such as the role of connectivity, morphology, biophysics and
187 neurogenesis. In the following paragraphs we review the most prominent of these models and
188 their predictions in relation to respective experimental findings.

189 **Exploring connectivity features in neuronal networks**

190 The Scharfman lab introduced a number of simple, biologically relevant, models of the
191 hippocampal DG-CA3 microcircuit (Myers and Scharfman, 2009, 2011; Myers et al., 2013;
192 Scharfman and Myers, 2015). In their first attempt, Myers and Scharfman used a simple network
193 model of the DG (Myers and Scharfman, 2009), consisting of GCs, mossy cells (MCs), HIPP cells
194 (HCs) and a general type of interneurons that played the role of basket (BCs) and chandelier
195 cells, all modeled as point neurons. The network was challenged against a simple pattern
196 separation task (i.e., distinguishing two input patterns with progressively increased overlap) in line
197 with a previous experimental study (Leutgeb et al., 2007). This relatively simple model had the
198 ability to discriminate highly overlapping patterns and predicted a role for hilar cells, MCs and
199 HCs, in pattern separation. Specifically, when MCs were completely removed from the model, the
200 GC population activity dropped to near-zero values, thus impairing pattern separation; however

201 when HCs were lesioned, GCs increased their activity and pattern separation improved. These
202 results appear to contradict previous theoretical analyses whereby increased GC sparsity
203 improved pattern separation. A possible explanation for this discrepancy lies in the distance metric
204 used to assess pattern separation, which did not take sparsity into account. Moreover, afferents
205 from MCs to interneurons and consequently, their inhibitory net effect (Jinde et al., 2012), were
206 not included in this first model.

207 In a follow up study, Myers and Scharfman used a new, sparsity-sensitive metric and extended
208 their model to incorporate the CA3 region and the back-projection from CA3 to DG, whose role in
209 pattern separation had not been explored at the time (Myers and Scharfman, 2011). The back-
210 projection was simulated as a connection between the principal CA3 neurons and DG hilar cells.
211 This modeling study was the first to propose that the back-projection improves pattern separation
212 by increasing the level of inhibition in the DG network. In line with these predictions, Faghihi and
213 colleagues recently showed that blockade of feedback inhibition to GCs in a probabilistic EC-DG
214 model, results in hyperexcitability in the DG which in turn, leads to pattern separation impairments
215 (Faghihi and Moustafa, 2015). The predicted role of inhibition in pattern separation has been
216 experimentally verified by (Engin et al., 2015).

217 The “simple DG-CA3 model” of Myers and Scharfman was also used to explore the effect of hilar
218 ectopic GCs (hEGCs) on pattern separation (Myers et al., 2013). In this case, adult-born GCs
219 (abGCs) mis-migrate into the hilar zone rather than into the granular layer. This phenomenon has
220 been reported to occur under seizure-induced neurogenesis in animal models, and hilar GCs
221 were found to share the same properties (i.e., membrane properties, firing behavior, morphology,
222 mossy fiber axon) with GCs in the granular zone (Scharfman et al., 2000). It was found that the
223 miss-direction of even a very small number of hEGCs (~5% of the total population) was sufficient
224 for pattern separation deficits to emerge in the model. Interestingly, while adding a small number
225 of hyperexcitable GCs in the granular zone had very little effect on pattern separation, the effect

226 of an equivalent number of these cells, placed ectopically in the hilar layer, was significant
227 primarily because these cells were strongly excited by the CA3 back-projection (Scharfman et al.,
228 2000, 2007). A similar deficit in pattern separation has been proposed to emerge due to the
229 formation of few “dominant” GCs (GCs that respond to all inputs) located within the granule cell
230 layer of the DG (Larimer and Strowbridge, 2008, 2010; Thind et al., 2008). While “dominant” GCs
231 do not affect the overall activity of the DG, pattern separation is significantly impaired in a network
232 model as these cells respond to all inputs, thus preventing the formation of separate DG
233 representations (Scharfman and Myers, 2015).

234 Beyond the static detection of activity patterns, incorporation of spike timing dependent plasticity
235 (STDP) in a simple neural network model of the DG-CA3 microcircuit revealed some of the
236 possible mechanisms that may underlie the learning of new versus the recall of previously stored
237 information (Nolan et al., 2011). The proposed model performed pattern-by-pattern separation,
238 namely it had the ability to choose between recalling an already known pattern and storing a new
239 one. Simulation results demonstrated that the activation of CA3 cells via PP inputs versus the
240 activation of the same CA3 cells via mossy fibers was sufficient to discriminate novel from known
241 input patterns, respectively (Treves and Rolls, 1992; Kesner, 2007; Treves et al., 2008).

242 In a different approach, Neher and colleagues developed a computational model of EC-DG-CA3-
243 CA1 hippocampal subregions and studied the effect of grid-like properties of EC inputs (Hafting
244 et al., 2005; Moser et al., 2008; Rolls, 2013) on pattern separation (Neher et al., 2015). They
245 found that Hebbian learning rules were not sufficient for implementing pattern separation in the
246 presence of grid-like input to the DG cannot. This was due to the place-field-like code in the CA3,
247 where patterns referring to nearby locations are very similar. On the contrary, these plasticity rules
248 facilitated the transformation of grid-like input from the EC to a place field in CA3, a prediction
249 supported by a number of studies (Si and Treves, 2009; Savelli and Knierim, 2010; Cheng and
250 Frank, 2011). These modeling findings are in contrast with the theoretical work of (Rolls, 1995)

251 and suggest that a competitive net is not a good candidate for orthogonalizing patterns derived
252 from grid-like inputs.

253 In sum, the above computational models lent further support to the hypothesis that DG plays a
254 role in pattern separation, not only by investigating the role of GCs, but also by accounting for the
255 DG connectivity among the dentate neuronal cells. Simulations showed that MCs are
256 indispensable players in DG's ability to distinguish overlapping patterns, while inhibitory neurons
257 enhance this ability. The CA3 back-projection enhances pattern separation in a healthy brain, yet
258 in cases of "ectopic" GC populations, such as those during temporal lobe epilepsy, it can play a
259 detrimental role. Note that in all of the abovementioned studies, while not always explicitly
260 mentioned, pattern separation deficits were correlated with changes in network sparsity.

261 **Studying the effects of neurogenesis on pattern separation**

262 Numerous computational studies have investigated how neurogenesis may contribute to learning
263 and memory (Chambers et al., 2004; Deisseroth et al., 2004; Becker, 2005; Appleby and Wiskott,
264 2009; Aimone et al., 2010; Appleby et al., 2011), including the abovementioned models of (Myers
265 et al., 2013; Scharfman and Myers, 2015) that accounted for hEGCs and the "dominant" GC
266 hypothesis, respectively. Specifically, given an elevated neurogenesis rate, some GCs were
267 proposed to form an "ectopic" hilar population (Scharfman et al., 2000), while abGCs in the
268 granule layer were considered to form a "dominant" GC population due to their high firing rates
269 (Nakashiba et al., 2012). In general, two main strategies were used to study neurogenesis in
270 these models: replacement of a fraction of GCs with abGCs or addition of abGCs.

271 According to the simulations of (Wiskott et al., 2006), absence of neurogenesis in a simple three-
272 layer feedforward artificial neural network led to catastrophic interference between similar inputs.
273 On the contrary, results from other models suggested that neurogenesis does not have a
274 significant contribution to pattern separation (Weisz and Argibay, 2009; Finnegan and Becker,

275 2015) but does help pattern completion (Weisz and Argibay, 2009). Interestingly, Weisz and
276 Argibay suggested that this finding is due to implementing neurogenesis as an addition of new
277 neurons, all of which are likely to be active for both input patterns, thus leading to pattern
278 separation deficiencies. Aimone and colleagues on the other hand investigated the role of
279 neurogenesis using a biologically complex model of the EC-DG circuitry. The DG consisted of
280 three feedback layers (BCs, hilar interneurons and MCs) and a granular layer, as well as an input
281 layer consisting of lateral and medial EC cells (Aimone et al., 2009). Their model predicts that
282 neurogenesis increases pattern separation for events separated in time, while patterns learned
283 at the same time have some degree of similarity (i.e., pattern integration) (Aimone et al., 2009).
284 In a recent model consisting of a two layer neural network of EC and DG subregions modeled
285 using integrate and fire neurons (Faghihi and Moustafa, 2016), the authors examined the role of
286 neurogenesis not only in GCs, but also in interneurons. Although there is some experimental
287 evidence that a portion of adult-born neurons become inhibitory cells in the hippocampus (Liu et
288 al., 2003), a later study did not find any adult-born inhibitory cells in the DG (Seri et al., 2004) and
289 further research is required to assess whether apart from excitatory GCs, other types of neurons
290 are born in the adult DG (Pierre-Marie Lledo, 2006). Despite the lack of direct experimental
291 evidence, the model predicts that a balanced neurogenesis rate in both excitatory and inhibitory
292 neurons is required in order for the network to perform efficient pattern separation. Increased
293 neurogenesis of interneurons leads to a sparser network, while increased neurogenesis of
294 excitatory cells has the opposite effect. These predictions further support the hypothesis that
295 sparsity is a key mediator of pattern separation efficiency in the DG.

296 In sum, computational models suggest that the role of neurogenesis in pattern separation
297 depends on the type, rate and amount of neuronal proliferation as well as the direction of
298 migration. For instance, in animal models of temporal lobe epilepsy, a dramatic increase in DG
299 neurogenesis has been detected and many of the abGCs were seen to mis-migrate “ectopically”

300 in the hilus (Mohapel et al., 2004). In such cases, the effect on pattern separation as predicted
301 with computational modeling would be severe (Scharfman et al., 2000, 2007) due to overly
302 increased excitability. However, normal levels of neurogenesis are expected to increase pattern
303 separation efficiency (Aimone et al., 2009), (Faghihi and Moustafa, 2016), in line with
304 experimental evidence (van Praag et al., 1999; Bolz et al., 2015). Again, tight control of GC
305 sparsity seems to play a critical role in these studies.

306 **The role of intrinsic and morphological properties of DG cells**

307 Among the factors that potentially affect pattern separation is the structure and biophysics of
308 granule cells. For example, pattern separation ability is impaired in epilepsy, where GCs fire
309 repeatedly (Young et al., 2009). Using a biophysically complex model of the DG consisting of the
310 four major neuronal cell (i.e., GCs, MCs, BCs, and HCs), Yim et al found that mossy fiber
311 sprouting and/or stronger PP input is sufficient to impair pattern separation (Yim et al., 2015).
312 However, under specific manipulations of the GC intrinsic properties (e.g. an increase in the
313 conductance of specific channels that reduced input resistance) these impairments could be
314 rescued suggesting that plasticity of intrinsic properties can also mediate pattern separation, in
315 line with experimental findings (Young et al., 2009). Furthermore, Hummos and colleagues have
316 developed a model of EC-DG-CA3 circuitry with simple Izhikevich-type neurons (Izhikevich, 2003,
317 2010) in order to investigate how hippocampus switches between pattern separation and
318 completion modes (Hummos et al., 2014), as suggested by previously described models
319 (Hasselmo et al., 1995; Hasselmo and Wyble, 1997; Meeter et al., 2004). By including more
320 realistic inhibition to the network, provided by BCs and HIPP cells in DG and BCs and oriens-
321 lacunosum moleculare in CA3, they found that high ACh levels lead to a reduction in the number
322 of bursting GCs while low and medium levels of ACh lead to long-lasting bursting in the CA3
323 network, yet inhibition from OLM interneurons can maintain network stability. They conclude that

324 high ACh levels induce high sparsity in the GC activity, enabling DG to successfully distinguish
325 highly overlapping patterns.

326 GCs have a very simple dendritic morphology compared to other principal neurons of the
327 hippocampus, thus a natural question to ask is how these dendrites affect pattern separation.
328 Recent modeling efforts have explored the possible contribution of dendrites in the DG function
329 (Ujfalussy et al., 2009; Tejada et al., 2012, 2014; Platschek et al., 2016), however they did not
330 study the effect of GC structure on pattern separation. Chavlis et al., recently used a simple
331 neuronal network of the DG consisting of four neuronal types (GCs, MCs, BCs and HCs) to show
332 that dendrites could contribute to pattern separation by controlling sparsity (Chavlis et al., 2016).
333 Inspired by the DG network model of (Myers and Scharfman, 2009), the simulated GCs were
334 extended to include experimentally constrained dendritic compartments of various numbers,
335 length and diameter. It was found that network models where the morphology of GC dendrites
336 varied achieved the same pattern separation performance when calibrated to exhibit the same
337 GC sparsity levels but not when calibrated to have for example the same input resistance. Similar
338 findings were seen when matching sparsity levels via a wide range of other mechanisms, either
339 intrinsic such as the leak conductance and the soma dimensions or extrinsic such as the synaptic
340 weight of EC inputs.

341 A variant of this model without GC cell dendrites was recently used to explain the role of MCs in
342 behavioral as well as neural pattern separation in awake behaving animals (Danielson et al.,
343 2017). It was predicted that MCs play a key role in pattern separation as evidenced in behavioral
344 experiments and recordings due to their net inhibitory effect.

345 Overall, these detailed modeling studies come to complement less complicated approaches by
346 providing mechanistic explanations for the various instantiations of pattern separation and its
347 deficits. Many of these predicted mechanisms in line or supported by experimental findings, others

348 are waiting to be tested. Activity sparsity of the DG network and various ways of controlling it is
349 once more highlighted as a key player.

350 **DISCUSSION**

351 The advent of technology over the last few years provided new, powerful tools both for probing
352 the brain experimentally and for simulating in sufficient detail the electrical activity of thousands
353 of neurons. Researchers are now able not only to simulate the hippocampus using larger, more
354 sophisticated models but also to include in these models neurons with biophysical and
355 morphological characteristics. Since Marr's mathematical model of hippocampal function, a large
356 number of predictions were generated, many of them validated by empirical data, others still open
357 to experimental testing, shedding new light to the mnemonic process of pattern separation.

358 Different types of models contributed differently to this endeavor. Early theoretical studies
359 suggested that the DG, which precedes the CA3 area in the hippocampus, acts as a competitive
360 network in order to transform the highly overlapping incoming information into a sparse yet
361 efficient (i.e., non-redundant) representation in CA3 principal neurons. This is a necessary
362 condition for the CA3 autoassociative network to operate efficiently and achieve a large storage
363 capacity (Rolls, 1989a; b; Treves and Rolls, 1992; Cerasti and Treves, 2010; Kesner and Rolls,
364 2015). To achieve this goal dentate GCs, the principal DG neurons, should be able to distinguish
365 among different input patterns, a prediction that has received substantial experimental support
366 (Leutgeb et al., 2007; McHugh et al., 2007; Nakashiba et al., 2012; Hunsaker and Kesner, 2013).

367 While early models were able to capture several features of pattern separation, they lacked the
368 ability to point the underlying mechanisms. Recent, more detailed neuron models generated a
369 number of mechanistic explanations (Ujfalussy et al., 2009; Tejada and Roque, 2014; Yim et al.,
370 2015; Chavlis et al., 2016; Platschek et al., 2016). For example, the dendrites of GCs were very

371 recently assigned a role in their ability to distinguish between similar inputs (Chavlis et al., 2016).
372 While dendrites have been suggested to serve as powerful computational units of pyramidal
373 neurons across various brain areas (Poirazi et al., 2003; London and Häusser, 2005; Sidiropoulou
374 et al., 2006; Spruston, 2008; Silver, 2010; Papoutsi et al., 2014), their role in pattern separation
375 is just starting to be addressed. Chavlis and colleagues (Chavlis et al., 2016) predicted that
376 dendrites, along with a number of other mechanisms such as synaptic strengths, somatic
377 dimensions, ionic conductances etc. contribute to pattern separation by controlling sparsity in the
378 GC population.

379 Several computational models have suggested that inhibition to GCs, either direct via
380 interneurons or indirect via the mossy-to-basket cell circuitry, facilitates pattern separation, a
381 prediction that has been experimentally verified (Jinde et al., 2012, 2013; Engin et al., 2015).
382 What remain unclear are the subcellular mechanisms by which inhibition exerts its powerful
383 actions. Are all inhibitory neurons acting in a similar manner? Does dendritic inhibition play a
384 different role compared to somatic inhibition? What do the dendrites of interneurons contribute to
385 pattern separation? All these questions are slowly beginning to be addressed in both models and
386 animals.

387 Neurogenesis is another promising and highly investigated feature of the DG. The current working
388 model views abGCs as a means for encoding new incoming information, thus increasing storage
389 capacity and enhancing the distinction between novel and already learned information. This idea
390 has received some support by empirical data (Deng et al., 2010; Bolz et al., 2015) but a lot
391 remains to be done in order to understand how and when abGCs are integrated into mature
392 circuits. Recently, it was proposed that abGCs are divided into two categories; the immature
393 abGCs and the mature abGCs (Johnston et al., 2016). The immature abGCs are hypothesized to
394 play the role of “pattern integrators”, while the mature ones to maximize GC activity sparsity.

395 Storage capacity in the DG is also something that needs further investigation, both in animals and
396 models. Most computational models study the ability to distinguish between just two input
397 patterns, a challenge much simpler than the one a real brain is faced with on a daily basis. In this
398 direction, recent computational approaches examine the ability of DG to discriminate similar
399 patterns while preserving their information content (Severa et al., 2016; Vineyard et al., 2016).
400 Specifically, Vineyard et al. (2016) predict that neurogenesis in the DG helps increase the
401 preservation of information content, albeit up to a saturation level, suggesting that adult
402 neurogenesis is essential not only for pattern separation, but also for preserving and even
403 increasing the information content of DG patterns.

404 The above computational and experimental studies highlight the complexity of the neural
405 substrate underlying the mnemonic process of pattern separation. The emerging picture suggests
406 that a wide range of network, cellular and sub-cellular mechanisms cooperate under a unifying
407 framework in order to control sparsity, the key determinant of pattern separation, in the DG
408 neuronal population (see **Figure 2**). A nature question that arises is why does the brain need so
409 many different mechanisms to mediate pattern separation? One possibility is to ensure flexibility
410 and enable adaptability. Given that pattern separation is critical for several different neural
411 functionalities, ranging from object recognition (Bakker et al., 2008; Ally et al., 2013; Bolz et al.,
412 2015) to navigation and context-dependent associative memory (Leutgeb et al., 2007; McHugh
413 et al., 2007; Clelland et al., 2009; Berron et al., 2016), the brain must ensure redundancy in terms
414 of its mechanistic substrate so as to maintain functionality even under degenerative conditions.
415 This flexibility can be achieved by having several readily accessible mechanisms to control
416 sparsity, and in turn pattern separation efficiency.

417 To conclude, while both CA3 and CA1 subregions have been extensively studied in terms of
418 connectivity and neurophysiology, the specific characteristics of DG circuits *in vivo* remain largely
419 unknown. This knowledge gap stems primarily from technical limitations that make it challenging

420 to record from DG neurons in behaving animals (Danielson et al., 2016). Computational
421 approaches are very useful for bridging the gap between the limited experimental evidence and
422 the possible functions of various DG neurons. As discussed in this review, a large number of
423 modeling predictions generated over the years have steered the interest of the scientific
424 community and received experimental support, while others remain under investigation. This on-
425 going exchange between theoreticians and experimentalists shows that computational models
426 can be used to frame hypotheses and drive experimental investigations in a more targeted and
427 efficient manner, thus facilitating the scientific discovery process. Given the advent of technology
428 on both fronts, the time is ripe for an even closer collaboration between theory and experiments.

429 **Acknowledgments:** This work was supported by the ERC Starting Grant dEMORY (2012-StG-
430 311435). P.P. would like to acknowledge support from the FENS-Kavli Network of Excellence.

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713

714 **FIGURE LEGENDS**

715 **Figure 1.** Schematic representation of the pattern separation function. **A.** Pattern separation using
716 population-based coding. When two highly overlapping EC inputs (input A, red triangles & input
717 B, blue triangles with identical mean firing rates) arrive in the DG, the corresponding outputs (red
718 & blue circles, respectively) are highly dissimilar. Overlap is denoted with symbols (cells) colored
719 with both red and blue. Note that the output pattern is highly sparse as few GCs encode any given
720 pattern. Here, pattern separation is estimated using the f_1 metric, which corresponds to the ratio
721 of the hamming distance (HD) between two compared patterns over the total number of cells
722 activated by both of these patterns. “ N ” denotes the size of the neuronal population where the
723 two patterns are expressed. For input patterns, N would be the size of the EC population while for
724 output patterns N would be the size of the DG population. “ s ” denotes the minimum sparsity (i.e.,
725 the minimum percentage of silent cells in the neuronal population where the two patterns are
726 expressed) and the subscripts denote the two compared patterns (input or output). Thus, f_1 is
727 calculated separately for the two input and the two output patterns. Pattern separation is achieved
728 whenever $f_{1,o}$ (distance of output patterns) is greater than $f_{1,i}$ (distance of input patterns). For the
729 example illustrated here the parameters are $N_i=16$, $s_i=\min(12,11)/16=11/16$ and $HD_i=3$, while
730 $N_o=100$, $s_o=\min(93, 91)/100=91/100$ and $HD_o=12$. Thus, $f_{1,i}=0.30 < f_{1,o}=0.67$, which means that the
731 two patterns are successfully separated at the output level. **B.** Pattern separation using rate-
732 based coding. When two highly overlapping EC inputs (input A & B, with different mean firing
733 rates but identical input populations) arrive in the DG, the corresponding outputs are highly
734 dissimilar in their firing rates but also likely to differ in the populations they activate. The distance
735 between a pair of patterns is estimated over the set of common neurons (circles colored with both
736 cyan and magenta) using the f_2 metric. f_2 assesses the ratio of the firing frequency rates of input
737 neurons (input A, input B) and common output neurons, namely those that are active in response
738 to both of these two patterns (output A, output B). The minimum value subtraction is for

739 normalization, and the subtraction from one transforms the similarity metric into a distance metric.
740 Again, using the formula for the example illustrated here and assuming that each neuron in the
741 two input patterns has a firing rate of $r_{i,A}=20\text{ Hz}$ and $r_{i,B}=30\text{ Hz}$, respectively, then $f_{2,i}=0.95$. If $r_{o,A}=4$
742 Hz and $r_{o,B}=5\text{ Hz}$, then $f_{2,o}=0.99$. Since $f_{2,o}$ is larger than $f_{2,i}$ the patterns are discriminated based on
743 rate coding. Note that the values of both f_1 and f_2 metrics range from 0 (identical patterns) to 1
744 (completely different patterns).

745 **Figure 2.** A unifying mechanistic framework for pattern separation. Schematic representation of
746 the proposed framework for mediating pattern separation through controlling sparsity levels in the
747 DG population. According to this working model, sparsity is the key determinant of pattern
748 separation. Sparsity is controlled by a number of sub-cellular (e.g. dendrites), cellular (e.g. GC
749 excitability) and network (e.g. connection strengths, inhibition) mechanisms. Additionally, pattern
750 separation is affected via other various parameters, such as the sparse connectivity between GCs
751 and CA3 principal neurons, the large number of GCs compared with EC and CA3 neurons, and
752 the function of neurogenesis.

A. Population Overlap

B. Rate Overlap

754 **Figure 2**

